

YUQORI YARIM TEKISLIK UCHUN KARLEMAN FORMULASI

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Annotatsiya: Maqola chegaralanmagan soha uchun Karleman formulasi haqida.

Kalit so'zlar: Soha, Lebeg o'lchov, puasson integrali, garmonik funksiya, golomorf, konform.

$D = \{z \in \mathbb{C} : \text{Im} z > 0\}$ soha chegaralanmagan yuqori yarim tekislik deb nomlanadi. Karleman formulasi ushbu soha uchun juda muhim hisoblanadi. $M \subset R = \partial D$ musbat Lebeg o'lchovli to'plam bo'lsin (chekli bo'lishi shart emas). Endi Puasson integralini qaraymiz:

$$U(x, y) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\chi_M(t) y dt}{(x-t)^2 + y^2}, \quad (1)$$

Ushbu funksiya D dagi garmonik musbat funksiya U ni aniqlaydi, chegaraviy qiymati R da χ_M uzluksizlikning barcha nuqtalarida χ_M bilan mos keladi. Agar

$$\int_M \frac{dt}{1+|t|} < \infty, \quad (2)$$

bo'lsa, u holda U ga qo'shma bo'lgan V funksiyani quyidagi formula bilan tuzish mumkin:

$$V(x, y) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{(x-t)\chi_M(t) dt}{(x-t)^2 + y^2}.$$

Agar (2) formula o'rinli bo'lmasa, u holda undan ham murakkabroq bo'lgan quyidagi formulani qo'llash mumkin:

$$V(x, y) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{x-t}{(x-t)^2 + y^2} + \frac{t}{t^2 + 1} \chi_M(t) dt.$$

Karleman g'oyasini ifodalash uchun “o’suvchi” funksiya hisoblanadigan $\varphi(z) = \exp(U + iV)$ golomorf funksiyani olamiz. Bizga ma’lum, $z \in D$ bo’lganda $\varphi \in H^\infty(\Pi)$ va $1 < |\varphi(z)| < e$.

Teorema 1. Agar $f \in H^p(D)$, $1 \leq p \leq \infty$ va $M \subset R = \partial D$ Lebeg musbat o’lchamlariga ega bo’lsa, u holda barcha $z \in D$ nuqta uchun D dagi kompaktdagi teng o’lchovli yaqinlashuvchi Karleman formulasi o’rinli bo’ladi.

$$f(z) = \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_M f(t) \left[\frac{\varphi(t)}{\varphi(z)} \right]^m \frac{dt}{t-z} \tag{3}$$

Isbot. Teorema isbotlash uchun dastlab integralni baholash zarur:

$$J_m = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{R/M} f(t) \left[\frac{\varphi(t)}{\varphi(z)} \right]^m \frac{dt}{t-z}, \tag{4}$$

R/M to’plamda $|\varphi(t)|$ funksiya deyarli har doim 1 ga teng; jumladan, Gelder tengsizligini qo’llanib (4) integral moduli uchun $\frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$, $p > 1$ baholashga ega bo’lamiz:

$$|J_m| \leq \frac{1}{2\pi |\varphi(z)|^m} \left[\int_{R/M} \frac{dt}{|t-z|^q} \right]^{1/q} \tag{5}$$

Bu yerda $m \rightarrow \infty$ bo’lsa $J_m \rightarrow \infty$, D dagi kompaktlarga teng o’lchovga ega ekanligi kelib chiqadi. Agar $p = 1$ bo’lsa, u holda

$$|J_m| \leq \frac{1}{2\pi |\varphi|^m \inf_{t \in R/M} |t-z|} \int_{R/M} |f(t)| dt, \tag{6}$$

va yana $m \rightarrow \infty$ da J_m nolga intilganda D dagi kompaktlarga teng o'lchamlilikka erishamiz. Teorema isbotlandi.

Bu teorema $p = \infty$ holda, (5) yoki (6) turdagi baholashning bo'lmaganligi uchun emas, balki $H^p(D)$ sinfdagi funksiyalar uchun Koshi integral formulasining yo'q ekanligi uchun ham qo'llanila olmaydi. Ammo, bu holatda Puasson formulasi o'rinli, ya'ni $f \in H^p(D), 1 \leq p \leq \infty$ bo'lsa, u holda barcha $z \in D$ uchun:

$$f(z) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{yf(t)dt}{(x-t)^2 + y^2}. \quad (7)$$

Puasson yadrosi R da absolyut integrallanuvchi, demak ushbu usul orqali quyidagini keltirishimiz mumkin.

Teorema 2. Agar $f \in H^p(D), 1 \leq p \leq \infty$ va M Lebeg musbat o'lchamlarga ega bo'lsa, u holda $z \in D$ uchun quyidagi formula o'rinli bo'lib, chegara D dagi kompaktlarda teng o'lchovlilikka erishadi,

$$f(z) = \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_M f(t) \left[\frac{\varphi(t)}{\varphi(z)} \right]^m \frac{ydt}{(x-t)^2 + y^2}. \quad (8)$$

Karleman formulasining ko'p o'lchamli analoglarining qaralib o'tilishi uchun D yarim tekisligidagi ushbu formula o'rinli bo'ladigan funksiyalar sinfini kengaytirish lozim. $F(w) = f\left(i \frac{1-w}{1+w}\right) \in H^p(U(0,1))$ funksiya uchun Karleman

formulasi faqatgina quyidagi vaziyatda o'rinli,

$$\frac{f(z)}{(z+t)^{2/p}} \in H^p(\Pi), \quad 1 \leq p \leq \infty. \quad (9)$$

Teorema 3. Agar $f \in A(D)$ funksiyasi (9) sha'rtini qanoatlantirsa va $M \subset R$ to'plam Lebeg musbat o'lchamlariga ega bo'lsa, u holda soha chegarasi D dagi kompaktlarda teng o'lchovlilikka erishadi va quyidagi formula o'rinli bo'ladi:

$$f(z) = \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \frac{z+i}{2\pi i} \int_M f(t) \left[\frac{\varphi(t)}{\varphi(z)} \right]^m \frac{dt}{(i+t)(t-z)}. \quad (10)$$

Isboti. Mayli funksiya $F(w) = f\left(i \frac{1-w}{1+w}\right)$ bo'lsin, u holda $F(w) \in H^p(U)$ va teorema 1 bo'yicha quyidagi Karleman formulasi o'rinli:

$$F(w) = \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_M F(\xi) \left[\frac{\varphi(\xi)}{\varphi(w)} \right]^m \frac{d\xi}{\xi-w}. \quad (11)$$

Bu yerda, $\bar{M} - U(0,1)$ aylanadagi D yarimtekislikning $w = (i-z)(i+z)^{-1}$ konform akslantirishdagi M ning aksi, $\bar{\varphi} - \bar{M}$ to'plam uchun φ rolini bajaradi. M.A.Lavrentev teoremasi bo'yicha $\bar{M}$ to'plam Lebeg musbat o'lchamli bo'lib hisoblanadi. Endi (11) formuladagi teskari akslantirishni amalga oshiramiz

$$\xi = \frac{i-t}{i+t}, \quad w = \frac{i-z}{i+z}$$

va bunda $\bar{M}$ garmonik o'lchovi M garmonik o'lchamga aylanishini, shu bilan birga $\bar{\varphi}$ funksiya φ ga o'tishini hisobga olsak, biz (10) formulaga o'tamiz. Teorema isbotlandi.

Teorema 4. M musbat Lebeg o'lchamining yopiq R qism to'plami bo'lsin. Quyidagini qaraymiz:

$$\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \frac{z+i}{2\pi i} \int_M f(t) \left[\frac{\varphi(t)}{\varphi(z)} \right]^m \frac{dt}{(i+t)(t-z)} = j(z). \quad (12)$$

Agar $f \in \overline{A^a}(\Pi)$ bo'lsa, u holda $z \in R/M$ uchun $J(z) = f(z)$ o'rinli va barcha $z \in M$ uchun har doim $J(z) = \frac{1}{2} f(z)$ bo'ladi, bunda (12) ni Koshi integrali bo'yicha asosiy qiymat sifatida tushunish kerak.

Isbot. Agar Teorema (4) chi shartni bajarsa va M to'plam chekli bo'lsa, u holda

$$f(\infty) = \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_M f(t) [\varphi(t)]^m \frac{dt}{t+i} \quad (13)$$

formula o'rinli. (13) formulaning isboti (4) dan kelib chiqadi va M chekli to'plam uchun quyidagiga ega bo'lamiz:

$$\varphi(z) = \exp \frac{i}{p} \int_M \frac{dt}{z-t} \quad (14)$$

Haqiqatdan ham, (14) tenglikdan $\varphi(\infty) = 1$ kelib chiqishini ko'rsatish yetarli.

Teorema isbotlandi.

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